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THE IMPACT OF THE ICT USAGE IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING ON CULTURAL ASSIMILATIVE PROCESSES OF THE COUNTRY

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Abstract. Over the history of its development, virtual means of communication have already left a significant mark on the formation of a modern authentic culture of any country. As their accessibility expands, the cultural boundaries between countries are blurring more every year. For successful orientation in the information space, students need to have an information culture. The article discusses the use of new information and communication technologies in teaching a foreign language in higher education. The relevance of the use of information and communication technologies in teaching a foreign language, which is pointed out by modern specialists, is demonstrated. The definition of the concept of "information and communication technologies" is given. The need to update views on the educational strategy is noted and modern trends and means in the use of information and communication technologies, such as: computer training, the Internet, e-books, audiobooks and audiovisual means are presented. These tools allow students to practice their language skills in real conditions and develop intercultural communication skills. The authors recommend that modern researchers pay more attention to the research of information and communication technologies. The opinion is expressed that it is necessary to gradually strengthen the cultural aspect of learning a foreign language in higher education, building education on a comparative analysis not so much of languages as of cultures of one's own country and the country of the language being studied.

Keywords: information and communication technologies, foreign languages, teacher, communicative competence, intercultural communication, assimilation

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ВЛИЯНИЕ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ИКТ ПРИ ИЗУЧЕНИИ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА НА АССИМИЛЯТИВНЫЕ ПРОЦЕССЫ В КУЛЬТУРЕ СТРАНЫ

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Аннотация. Виртуальные средства коммуникации за историю своего развития уже оставили значительный след в формировании современной аутентичной культуры любой страны. По мере расширения их доступности культурные границы между странами размываются сильнее с каждым годом. Для успешного ориентирования в информационном пространстве обучающимся необходимо владеть информационной культурой. В статье рассматривается вопрос применения новых информационно-коммуникативных технологий в обучении иностранному языку в высшей школе. Продемонстрирована актуальность использования информационно-коммуникативных технологий в преподавании иностранного языка, на которую указывают современные специалисты. Дано определение понятия «информационно-коммуникативные технологии». Отмечается потребность в обновлении взглядов на образовательную стратегию и представлены современные тенденции и средства в использовании информационно-коммуникативных технологий, такие как: компьютерное обучение, Интернет, электронные книги, аудиокниги и аудиовизуальные средства. Эти инструменты позволяют обучающимся практиковать свои языковые навыки в реальных условиях и развивать навыки межкультурного общения. Авторы рекомендуют современным исследователям уделять больше внимания исследованиям информационно-коммуникативных технологий. Выражается мнение необходимости постепенно усиливать культурологический аспект изучения иностранного языка в высшей школе, выстраивая обучение на сопоставительном анализе не столько языков, сколько культур собственной страны и страны изучаемого языка.

Ключевые слова: информационно-коммуникативные технологии, иностранные языки, преподаватель, коммуникативная компетенция, межкультурная коммуникация, ассимиляция

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Information and communication technologies have long changed the habitual way of human life in the XXI century, revolutionizing industries such as healthcare, finance, education and entertainment. A number of digital tools, systems and services that are used to access, process, store and transmit information are included in information and communication technologies. These technologies also include computers, smart phones, the Internet, social networks, e-mail, video conferencing and various software applications.

The issue of the use of new ICT in teaching a foreign language is increasingly being addressed in scientific circles. In expanding the educational space of modern higher education, information and communication technologies are considered one of the most effective. We would like to note the important fact that information and communication technologies have allowed people from all over the world to connect and communicate with each other in real time, overcoming time and distance barriers.

This article is about the usage of ICTs to reveal the cultural aspect of intercultural communication while learning a foreign language. Our main task is to focus on its potential in teaching a foreign language in higher education based on the study of works that are devoted to the basic provisions of the use of ICTs. First of all, we wanted to pay attention to the correct use of ICT in the modern classroom.

To begin with, it is important to highlight that we are currently witnessing the emergence of a new type of personality among our graduates. This new breed is characterized by their openness to the latest trends in modernity and social order. The capacity for success in diverse fields of expertise for future professionals relies heavily on their ability to swiftly adjust to varying socio-cultural circumstances. In today's world, it is essential to respond appropriately to public influence and possess the ability to shape it accordingly. To speak foreign languages proficiently, one must acknowledge and comprehend the disparities between their own culture and those of foreign cultures. Put simply, modern individuals embody their national culture while simultaneously adapting to intercultural surroundings.

We can confidently state that the significance and role of language in shaping an individual's person-

ality within the context of information and communication culture is becoming increasingly pertinent. Language, in this context, is perceived as a distinct realm in which the personality is fully immersed. The acquisition of multiple languages simultaneously entails the exploration of new worlds replete with unique ethnic and cultural specifics.

Undoubtedly, the existence of linguistic and cultural adaptation cannot be refuted, nor can the challenge of reconciling language, personality and culture. The main goal of the education and upbringing system is successful adaptation. The modern world places high demands on a graduate of a higher school and today scientists and methodologists agree that the formation of communicative and intercultural competence is the main goal of learning a foreign language, noting that the use of ICT is considered an important approach in its implementation. Back in the 80s, there was great interest in the use of ICT, communicative theories were developed, and a communicative approach to teaching was practiced. A substantial contribution to the development and use of ICT in foreign language classes was made by: A.A. Andreev, V.A. Bubnov, S.G. Grigoriev, S.A. Zhdanov, P.V. Sysoev and other academic teachers.

Attempts to study personality and culture through the prism of language have been made for a long time. In such studies, culture invariably holds a central position, particularly in regards to its customs, rituals, upbringing practices, and familial dynamics. Socio-cultural space is the coverage of cultural meanings of the whole set of activities and relationships of people. The features of such a space include the integration of all spheres of life, the activation of intercultural relations, the growth of communications, the development of a special information subspace open to all. Thus, intercultural dialogue acts as a defining component, and language - as a tool for building a new cultural environment.

Language acts as an instrument of cultural formation of personality in the modern communicative paradigm. While learning a language, a world of culturally significant subjects opens up. Communication with a native speaker or intercultural communication helps to look at your native culture from the outside.

Intercultural communication is involved in the formation of a modern type of personality.

L.A. Artemyeva believes that intercultural discourse should focus on the pragmatic aspect. The author explains this as pragmatics, to which an ethical aspect is added, "implying moral values, knowledge of situational realities, understanding of semantic associations and connotations, norms of speech behavior of native speakers, especially relevant in a situation of real communication" [Artemyeva]. The reflection of the foreign world and culture is found in every foreign word, and each language structure preserves a national idea of the world, its character and mentality. "It is necessary to learn to understand the unity of language and culture and better navigate the array of cultural information that is objectively reflected in the language" [2].

If the training of students of narrow philological specialties is aimed at studying intercultural communication, linguoculturology, neuro-linguistics, sociolinguistics, country studies, etc., then other areas of training (43.03.02 "Tourism", 43.03.03 "Hotel business", 38.03.02 "Management" (focus: International Management), 38.03.01 "Economics" (Profile "World Economy")). In foreign language classes, it is essential to acquire a background understanding of the country where the language is spoken, including their history and culture. This information is acquired through various methods and is often discussed in conjunction with the language's linguistic components. A key consideration is that some of the above training areas study two foreign languages.

O.I. Burkova, exploring understanding in intercultural communication, considers it a prerequisite for effective intercultural interaction. As noted by the author the lack of understanding entails rejection of communication partners, rejection of a different culture, conflicts. The success of intercultural communication depends on the level and quality of understanding. The author calls cultural and linguistic factors significant in achieving understanding between the participants of communication. The language is the conductor of culture, because it reflects the peculiarities of culture. "The content of the partner's speech in intercultural communication, focused on establishing contact, represents the process of transformation, awareness and transformation of social, interpersonal characteristics into intrapersonal

ones" [3]. Cultural and linguistic differences are the causes of misunderstanding.

We should consider not only the individual, personal, psychological characteristics in intercultural interactions, of the speaker, but also the fact that representatives of different cultures have different ideas about the norms of behavior and traditions. It is highly important to understand the communication partner as a representative of someone else's culture, whose culture is significantly different from the native one. "Teaching foreign languages as a means of communication between representatives of different peoples and cultures is that languages should be studied in inseparable unity with the world and culture of the peoples speaking these languages" [9]. However, we all make some mistakes when speaking a foreign language, which is usually perceived good-naturedly by native speakers. But cultural mistakes are unforgivable and produce the most negative impression.

Nevertheless, such mistakes are becoming less frequent due to the development of modern technologies and their widespread introduction into the educational process. In addition to the controlled use of ICT in the classroom, students independently use such technologies in everyday life.

Unrestricted and uncontrolled access to the information environment can cause imperceptible, but no less alarming changes in the minds of future professionals, their attitude to the culture of their country and the countries of "global", "generally accepted" communication languages.

To prevent any negative consequences, we need an extremely clear idea of modern technologies, their work, and the opportunities they provide not only in the classroom, but also in students' free time.

Thus, here the authors consider it justified to consider in detail the concept of ICT and their role in the learning system.

At the present stage, numerous distinct methods for designating already exist of ICTs. For example, Y.G. Yakovleva defines ICT as the nature of student-teacher interaction, the organization of independent research work and a tool for structuring and systematizing knowledge [13]. In the dictionary of verbal usage, edited by L.M. Lumzina, ICT is "a set of means and methods of converting information, data to obtain information of a new quality (information product)" [5].

In the Pedagogical Dictionary of G.M. Kojaspirov and A.Yu. Kojaspirova ICT is "methods and means of obtaining, converting, transmitting, storing and using information" [4].

Therefore, we understand the term "information and communication technologies" as an interactive and dynamic nature that has sufficient stability of an individual student, providing opportunities to guide his learning and receive information. ICTs provide faster, more efficient and cost-effective information exchange and cooperation.

In the Order of the Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation dated 17.12.2010 No. 1897 (ed. dated 31.12.2015) "On approval of the Federal State educational standard of basic general education" [1] the following aspects related to "Foreign Language" are emphasized, specifically:

- 1) comprehending the socio-cultural characteristics of the country where the target language is spoken (the ability to distinguish common and different in the native culture);
- 2) formation of communicative competence (speech, language, socio-cultural, compensatory, educational and cognitive);
- 3) achievement of the threshold level of foreign language proficiency;
- 4) to form the skills of translation from a foreign language into Russian;
- 5) the formation of educational and research skills. Consequently, "on the part of the teacher, increased attention is required to the organization of the educational process to achieve such educational results as: personal, meta-subject and subject" [1].

For example, E. V. Timofeeva, Yu. A. Kail in their research claim that modern education has long been built on digital technologies that are used to create and transmit information. When using ICT in the classroom, students are given not just ready-made knowledge, skills, and habits, but the ability of self-education is instilled. The authors note the advantages of using ICT in the classroom, namely: general cultural development; improvement of language level and computer skills; motivation and development of interest in the subject being studied; individualization of learning; development of independent work skills.

Especially the authors emphasize that the teacher in working with ICT needs to remember the following: "a computer in the educational process is not a mechanical teacher, not a substitute teacher, but an active means of developing students, strengthening and expanding the possibilities of their cognitive activity" [12]. Consequently, regular use of ICT in foreign language classes will form students' independent work skills and increase motivation to learn.

N.V. Shishonina sets a goal in her research to correspond to modern information and ICTs in teaching a foreign language at school. A number of didactic tasks are solved with the help of the Internet, for example, using the materials of the global network, students "develop reading skills and abilities, improve written speech, replenish vocabulary, and most importantly, a stable motivation to study is formed" [10]. Moreover, Internet technologies broaden the horizons of students; contribute to establishing and maintaining communication with peers around the world.

The author leads us to the idea that in order to successfully navigate the information space, students need to have information culture and suggest considering basic resources such as: e-mail (e-mail), video conferences, the creation and possibility of publishing their own page on the web (homepage), search engines, reference catalogs and online conversation. Summing up, the author argues that it is impossible to form communicative and intercultural competence without real communication practice. Students are given the opportunity to have authentic communication with native speakers on current topics using the Internet in a foreign language lesson. The teacher needs to competently integrate the use of ICT in the classroom.

F.M. Muminova argues that modern ICTs and the possibility of their use in teaching are available to all teachers; the main thing is to interest students in learning. The author also emphasizes that the use of ICT will increase motivation, and a foreign language lesson will have a practical result – on the formation of communicative competence [6]. The author sees the use of ICT in the classroom as an opportunity to diversify the learning process; students will receive more visual and perceptible mate-

rial. The importance of using audio and video material in the classroom is noted, which makes it meaningful.

The author calls for a harmonious combination of traditional teaching methods with ICT at all stages. Consequently, the effectiveness of teaching will increase many times; students will receive an impetus to further independent language learning.

L.Y. Mirzoeva and Zh.B. Yerzhanova also consider information and communication technologies as one of the key topics of their scientific research. Answering the question "Why is it necessary to use ICT in the classroom?" the authors focus our attention on the following: motivation, interactivity of learning, flexibility of individual mode of work, freedom of action and independence, accessibility, practice of authentic communication, feedback [7]. Digital educational resources facilitate mass access to educational materials, regardless of time and space constraints. E-learning presents unlimited opportunities for teaching a foreign language.

On the contrary, M.V. Plaskina emphasizes "the growing inclination towards leveraging computers and the internet to improve the efficiency of teaching. There are several rapidly evolving ICT instruments, such as laptops, interactive whiteboards, multimedia projectors, the internet, and social networks" [7]. "The World Wide Web is an accessible collection of authentic materials created specifically for native speakers; therefore, they provide information about the culture of the country of the language being studied. Compared to the printed version, this type of information is the most relevant, as it is provided in real time" [8].

As we have tried to show, any approach and method of teaching is complemented and enriched with the use of ICT. It is impossible not to agree that ICTs provide more opportunities for communication between students of the same age. With the use of ICT, there is a two-way exchange of knowledge between the house and the university. It is essential that the teacher is the key to the successful use of ICT for learning. There is a need to update the views on the educational strategy. Education should be focused on "the development of the student's consciousness, his ability to think critically, independently determine his place in the communicative space of the micro and macro society" [8].

Today, students can access a large number of online resources and tools to improve their language proficiency and to enrich cultural awareness. Authentic materials and mass media from the studied linguistic cultures are open to students. Students can watch movies and TV shows, listen to music and podcasts, as well as read online news and literature in the language being studied, getting acquainted with authentic ways of communication and cultural practices.

Nevertheless, the widespread use of ICT has a downside, namely, the independent immersion of students in the culture. Against the background of rapidly developing globalization, such immersion can cause the focus of students' attention to shift from the development and enrichment of their own culture to the consumption of "alien" culture, where preference will be given to other people's values, opinions, and guidelines.

In the current political and economic conditions, this cannot be perceived as a positive factor affecting the culture of our country.

Among the current trends and means in the use of ICT, striking examples are: 1) computer language learning, in which the computer acts as an incentive that generates analysis, discussion and writing; 2) The Internet, which involves learning a language anywhere and at any time, expands opportunities and horizons.

Both in the first and in the second case, students find themselves in an information environment devoid of control over the consumption and perception of information. Here it is worth noting the role of the teacher, his authority and the ability not so much to competently apply ICT in their classes to facilitate the cognitive processes of students, but to competently teach students to process, filter and realize the difference between the foreign culture and their own. To do this, it makes sense to refract any use of ICT through the prism of bringing benefits for one's own cultural enrichment.

In addition, many language learning applications and software include artificial intelligence and machine learning algorithms to personalize learning and provide immediate feedback on grammar, pronunciation, and vocabulary usage. This allows students to work at their own pace and receive personalized feedback tailored to their individual needs.

As artificial intelligence develops, it becomes obvious that there is a trend in working with it, a vector for the development of information technologies in the near future. It is necessary to understand that artificial intelligence algorithms already at this stage carry certain attitudes, the significance of which cannot be denied. Such attitudes can also have both a positive and a negative impact on the processes of perception of foreign culture and the skills of intercultural communication of future specialists.

The use of artificial intelligence in the classroom, and even more so when encouraging students to work independently with artificial intelligence, should pay special attention not only to the source and developer of artificial intelligence, but also to the skills of working with it in modern conditions.

Virtual communication tools such as video conferencing, e-mail, and instant messaging also allow students to communicate with native speakers and other students from around the world, facilitating cross-cultural exchange and collaboration. These tools allow students to practice their language skills in the real-world settings and develop intercultural communication skills.

Over the history of its development, virtual means of communication have already left a significant mark on the formation of a modern authentic culture of any country. As their accessibility expands, the cultural boundaries between countries are blurring more every year. There is an opinion that such a virtual wave of information and cultural globalization is the most powerful in the history of mankind. And despite the fact that it is virtually impossible to preserve the authentic culture of the country in the conditions of the development of virtual means of communication, it remains only to make this process as conscious as possible. To do this, we need to strengthen the cultural aspect in higher education, building training on a comparative analysis of not so much languages as cultures of their country and the foreign culture.

It is impossible to stop the uncontrolled use of virtual means of communication by students outside of classroom classes, but it is possible to teach students how to use these means correctly by clearly setting the goals of using means of communication: the practical application of intercultural communication skills,

thereby preventing assimilative processes in their own culture.

We also want to offer the use of an e-book, which is a kind of electronic version of a traditional printed book that can be read using a personal computer or an e-book reader, such as an iPod. E-books improve classroom teaching skills, because you can add images, information graphics, video, text, audio, and so on to them. Students will develop note-taking skills, grammar and applied skills.

Moreover, books are among the positive factors of intercultural exchange, since they do not allow you to rapidly absorb any momentary information, but encourage analysis, reflection, and train perception. That, in addition to strengthening the cultural creates cultural self-awareness.

Online dictionaries that help to understand the meanings of many unknown words. Unlike the paper version, online dictionaries have a fairly convenient and fast navigation. Students have the opportunity to listen to a word and fix a new vocabulary.

Let's move on to audio books and audiovisual media; they develop four language systems: phonological, semantic, syntactic and pragmatic. The phonological system of a language is an organized set of phonemes that are connected by certain relationships, where each element cannot exist in isolation, but exists in connection with other elements. The semantic system of a language is an information model of a certain anthropocentric reflection and interpretation. Depending on the circumstances of life, the semantic system differs in different languages, in accordance with the culture of the inner and outer world of its speakers. The syntactic system reflects the stage of the grammatical structure of the language that forms coherent speech. The pragmatic system is close to the functional study of language in speech, is a special kind of semantics of language signs and reflects the "egocentric factor" in the language system.

It is important to acknowledge that one of the primary obstacles is the language barrier, which can negatively impact their psychological state. However, modern technologies enable teachers to conduct classes that are engaging, captivating, and informative despite this challenge. [9]. "Authentic audio materials are a sample of speech and language, special and general cultural vocabulary that contribute to accelerated and

effective assimilation of material in foreign language classes" [9]. Watching videos with subtitles at the initial stage enriches the vocabulary, which further facilitates the process of both viewing and reading.

Thus, we consider it necessary to summarize the advantages and disadvantages of ICT from the point of view of the linguistic aspect of learning a foreign language directly.

The advantages of ICT in foreign language classes include:

- 1) access to a variety of authentic materials and media from the studied language cultures;
- 2) personalization of learning, which provides feedback on grammar, pronunciation and vocabulary use through the use of artificial intelligence and machine learning algorithms;
- 3) the opportunity for virtual communication with native speakers;
- 4) increases the motivation of students, making language learning more exciting and interactive.

We consider the disadvantages of ICT:

- 1) the lack of the level of social interaction and human connections that is possible through personal communication, which can be an important aspect of language learning;
- 2) teachers rely on technology and neglect the importance of language learning strategies and good teaching practices;
- 3) ICTs create a digital divide between those who have access to technology and those who don't have it;
- 4) some students are distracted, which leads to a lack of concentration or involvement in the material.

Therefore technology can be a valuable tool for language learning, it should not replace face-to-face communication and interaction with people in a language classroom. Effective language teaching still requires qualified

teachers who can develop engaging and meaningful lessons that properly integrate technology and provide students with opportunities to interact with each other and with native speakers in real-world settings.

Before ICT was introduced, only a teacher, a blackboard and chalk participated in teaching a foreign language. However, having studied recent studies, we see that the learning process can be much more motivating and interesting using ICT. As the above review and discussion have shown, ICTs can help in various areas of learning. In addition, the discussion also reminds current researchers to pay more attention to ICT research as well.

Regarding the cultural dimension of acquiring a foreign language, specifically the development of intercultural communication and the broader influence of ICT on the country's culture, it is noteworthy how rapidly and seamlessly ICT is integrated into the educational sphere. However, the pace of this transformation does not afford us the luxury of pausing and thoughtfully evaluating the effects of ICT on the cultural evolutions occurring within the country.

The traces of information technology already left on the culture of our country, and we can conclude that if the process of introducing and using ICT remains without due attention to the view of assimilative processes, there is a risk that the culture of our country will be completely deformed under the culture of globalization, the culture of dominant language. And, despite the fact that these processes do not always carry danger, it is difficult to deny the need for careful study of this problem and search for ways to mitigate the impact of dominant cultures and change the vector of development of one's own culture from non-stop absorption to reasonable consumption of alien culture and enrichment at its expense.

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